

CURE KINETIC OF ADHESIVE FOR RAPID REPAIR BY NON-ISOTHERMAL METHOD

WANG Mengyuan

(School of Material Science and Engineering, North University of China, Taiyuan,
Shanxi, China 030051)

WANG Mengyuan (e-mail: phoenixwmy@126.com)

Abstract

Adhesive for the rapid repair is a new kind of epoxy resins, which has been applied in the pipe repairmen. The working principle of this kind of epoxy resin adhesive is utilizing the strong protective cover after its curing process. In order to study the relationship between physical properties and chemical structure, and analysis control of curing extent and curing conditions. Non-isothermal differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was implemented to measure the process for research on curing kinetic reaction mechanism of epoxy resin adhesive system at different heating rates at nitrogen atmosphere. The kinetic parameter of the curing process is followed Mákel method in iso-conversional condition. According to the data obtained by the experiment, following Kissinger Iteration Method, value of E_a can be figured out, $E_a = 42086.85\text{J/mol}$. Two parameters (m , n) of mechanism function can be calculated out, $n=0.7103$, $m=0.358962$. The theoretically calculated model shows a same result with the non-isothermal DSC curves from experimental data.

Keywords: curing kinetic, DSC, adhesive for rapid repair, Mákel method

1. Introduction

Epoxy resins have concentrated widely in recent years, and many investigations on the method of synthesis, curing process, and the thermosetting property have been reported. Therefor the researches on theoretical calculation concerning epoxy resins field provide basic supporting for the further study.

Adhesive for rapid repair is a new type of epoxy resin adhesive, which would have potential to be applied on the tiny break of closed aqueduct, heat supply system and sewage pipe network system, etc. in the near future. Date back to a few years ago, for pipe repairing, digging a wide area of soil or the thick protective covers with a large amount of waste on time and money, is common in daily life.

Actual simplification of maintenances boost adhesive for rapid repair emerged. This kind of adhesive is a fast solidifying epoxy adhesive with the advantage of easy operations and free pollutions. After curing process, the product has cement strength, and enjoys the outstanding properties of aging resistant, water resistant, weak acid and weak base resistant, and low rates of shrinkage and insulation.

It is a well-known fact that the physical and mechanical properties of cured epoxy resin adhesives rely on thermosetting structure, the curing degree, the curing condition including temperature and the time of the whole curing process. Hence in order to control the mean time to repair and instruct development of production industrially, the study of curing kinetic on adhesive for rapid repair is significant.

2. Non-isothermal kinetic analysis by DSC measurements

The curing process of adhesive for rapid repair was studied by non-isothermal

differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) technique at the different heating rates(5, 10, 20, 40 K/min), which heated from 30 to 300 °C in nitrogen atmosphere.

Groups of data can be obtained from the DSC experiments; results of testing were the data of the relationship between heating rate and the temperature. The experiment curves are as Fig.1:

Fig.1 Dynamic DSC of adhesive rapid repair

The data showed that there is a exothermic reaction peak from 32.7°C to 224.5°C for adhesive for rapid repair and temperature of the peak is 118.2 at 10°C/min heating rate, which confirmed main reaction of this kind of adhesive.

The curing process temperatures such as gelation temperature (T_{gel}) = 32.4°C, curing temperature (T_p) = 100.3°C and post-curing (T_{treat}) = 153.6°C were acquired by DSC technique at various heating rates.

The vital kinetic parameter of the curing process--- E_a , A , $f(\alpha)$ in this research can be deduced by the following steps in Mákel method. Following Kissinger-iterative Method and Ozawa-iterative Method, value of E_a can be figured out, $E_a = 42086.85\text{J/mol}$, which is determined by isoconversional method.

3. Results and discussion

3.1.1 Theory and Assumption

The curing kinetic process of the thermoset polymer in DSC technique follows three basic assumptions:

Exothermic area of DSC curve is proportional to total exothermal quantity of curing reaction.

The rate of the kinetic reaction is proportional to the rate of measured heat flow:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{dH}{dt} \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta H}$$

in which $\frac{d\alpha}{dt}$ is the rate of the kinetic reaction, $\frac{dH}{dt}$ is the rate of measure heat flow,

ΔH is the enthalpy of the curing reaction.

The equation of kinetic reaction rate can be express as following:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K(T)f(\alpha)$$

Especially pay attention, the rate of the kinetic reaction in the curing process is represented the curing degree. So in above-mentioned equation, α is curing degree, and $f(\alpha)$ is the function of α , which is determined by the curing mechanism. $K(T)$ is the rate constant, which conforms to Arrhenius Equation:

$$K(T) = Ae^{-\frac{E_a}{RT}}$$

where A is the pre-exponential factor and E_a is the apparent activation energy.

3.1.2 Calculate the kinetic parameter by the most probable function method from Mákel

So far, there have been diversiform methods of kinetic calculation applied to the practical field. The conditions of different kinds of method are various, therefore, we should consider the special occasion of each methods. This paper introduces Mákel method by iso-conversional, a mature method applied in kinetic analysis, to find kinetic parameters of the thermal treatment.

The vital kinetic parameter of the curing process--- E_a , A , $f(\alpha)$ in this research can be deduced by the following steps in Mákel method.

3.2.2.1 Calculate E_a by isoconversional method:

Following Kissinger Iteration Method, we get two functions; one of them is Kissinger Equation, as following:

Kissinger Equation:

$$\ln \left[\frac{\beta}{T^2} \right] = \ln \left[\frac{AR}{EG(\alpha)} \right] - \frac{E_a}{RT}$$

Another is Kissinger Iteration Equation, which is shown as follow:

Kissinger Iteration Equation:

$$\ln \left[\frac{\beta}{Q_4(u)T^2} \right] = \ln \left[\frac{AR}{EG(\alpha)} \right] - \frac{E_a}{RT}$$

u in iteration equation is:

$$u = \frac{E_a}{RT}$$

$Q_4(u)$ function is a approximated model using the 4th reasonable expression from Senum and Yang, described as follow:

$$Q_4(u) = \frac{u^3 + 18u^2 + 88u + 96}{u^4 + 20u^3 + 120u^2 + 240u + 120}$$

The difference between two kinds of above-mentioned equation, Kissinger Equation and Kissinger Iteration Equation, is that the former is influenced by the value of u . Using the former equation--- Kissinger Equation, value of E_{a1} can be figured out, $E_{a1}=80300.69$ J/mol.

However, the latter equation, Kissinger Iterative Equation, is considered the influence of $Q_4(u)$ changing along with u . Using E_{a1} as the initial value, we can calculate the new value of $Q_4(u)$, then work out the new value of E_{a2} again. By subsequent iteration, we get $E_{ai}(i=1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$. Finally $E_{ai} - E_{a(i-1)}$ will less than 0.1kJ/mol. This is a reasonable value of E_a . The value of E_{ai} is listed in the Table.1.

Determining the kinetic model

With the most probability mechanism function method given by Mákel, it is necessary

to appeal to two special functions $y(\alpha)$ and $z(\alpha)$.

$$y(\alpha) = \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dT}\right) e^x \quad (1)$$

$$z(\alpha) = \pi(x) \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt}\right) \frac{T}{\beta} \quad (2)$$

in function(2), $\pi(x)$ function is a approximated model using the 4th reasonable expression from Senum and Yang, described as follow:

$$\pi(x) = \frac{x^3 + 18x^2 + 88x + 96}{x^4 + 20x^3 + 120x^2 + 240x + 120} \quad (3)$$

The difference between two kinds of above-mentioned equation, Kissinger Equation and Kissinger Iteration Equation, is that the former is influenced by the value of u . Using the former equation---- Kissinger Equation, value of E_{a1} can be figured out, $E_{a1}=80300.69$ J/mol.

However, the latter equation, Kissinger Iterative Equation, is considered the influence of $Q_4(u)$ changing along with u . Using E_{a1} as the initial value, we can calculate the new value of $Q_4(u)$, then work out the new value of E_{a2} again. By subsequent iteration, we get $E_{ai}(i=1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$. Finally $E_{ai} - E_{a(i-1)}$ will less than 0.1kJ/mol. This is a reasonable value of E_a . The value of E_{ai} is listed in the Table.1.

Table.1 the value of E_{ai}

E_{ai}	Value of E_{ai}
E_{a1}	41714.25
E_{a2}	42089.49
E_{a3}	42086.85

Fig.2 Three times calculated value of E_{ai}

3.2.2.2 Determining the kinetic model

With the most probability mechanism function method given by Mákel, it is necessary to introduce two special functions $y(\alpha)$ and $z(\alpha)$.

$$y(\alpha) = \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dT}\right) e^u$$

$$z(\alpha) = Q_4(u) \left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} \right) \frac{T}{\beta}$$

$y(\alpha)$ is proportional to $f(\alpha)$, which is represent the characteristic of the kinetic model. The shape and maximum of $y(\alpha)$ and $z(\alpha)$ can be used to determine the most suitable kinetic model. Fig.5 and Fig.6 exhibit the value of $y(\alpha)$ and $z(\alpha)$ which were normalized within (0, 1).

Fig.3 $y(\alpha)$

Fig.4 $z(\alpha)$

These two functions give two maximal values respectively, and the maximum matching curing degree are α_M and α_P^∞ . Different β has different value of α_M and α_P^∞ , as following (Table.2):

Table.2 the value of α_P , α_M and α_P^∞ from thermo-grams analysis

β	α_M	α_P^∞	α_P
5	0.29218	0.59825	0.5836

10	0.30841	0.58501	0.5746
20	0.38956	0.54444	0.5373
40	0.35267	0.57518	0.5616
Mean	0.33571	0.57572	0.5643

α_p is the peak rate of kinetic process of DSC thermo-grams.

From Table.2, α_M and α_p^∞ is independent with heating flowing rate, meanwhile the value of α_p^∞ is lower than 0.6322. The shape of the function and these eigenvalues indicated that the curing reaction can be expressed as Seatal-Berggren Method, which is two parameters autocatalytic kinetic model. The equation is shown as follow:

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^m(1 - \alpha)^n$$

3.2.2.3 Calculate exponents

m and n are the kinetic exponents. The value of n can be figure out by the slope of $\ln\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} e^u\right)$ versus $\ln[\alpha^p(1 - \alpha)]$, $p = \frac{\alpha_M}{1 - \alpha_M}$, simultaneity $p = \frac{m}{n}$. Subsequently, the value of m can be fixed down. Table.3 exhibits the kinetic parameters calculated by aforementioned step:

Table.3 The value of kinetic parameters calculated for the curing reaction

β	m	n	LnA
5	0.360175	0.7127	12.347
10	0.348602	0.6898	12.427
20	0.365885	0.7240	12.465
40	0.361186	0.7147	12.566
Mean	0.358962	0.7103	12.45125

3.2.2.4 Calculate pre-exponential factor

By utilizing the value of E_a and the kinetic model, the pre-exponential factor A can be work out as the under mentioned equation:

$$A = -\frac{\beta u_p}{T_p f'(\alpha_p)} e^{u_p}$$

in which $f'(\alpha)$ is differential coefficient form of $f(\alpha)$.

Table.4 shows the value of the pre-exponential factor A:

Table.4 The value of the pre-exponential factor A

β	A
5	230268.20103
10	249446.56428
20	259107.93725
40	286645.05867
Mean	255569.58503

3.3 curing kinetic mechanism function

According to the calculated kinetic parameter above, the curing kinetic mechanism function of TMBP/DDM system can be fixed down ultimately. The function is as follow:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dT} = A\alpha^{0.358962}(1 - \alpha)^{0.7103} \exp\left(\frac{-42086.85}{RT}\right)$$

3.4 Comparison of computer simulated data with experiment data

The theoretically calculated model shows a same result with the DSC curves from experimental data, which is shown as Fig.7. This research result can be chose as the theory of practical production.

Fig.5 Comparison of experimental data and simulate data for TMBP/DDM epoxy resin

4 Conclusions

According to the DSC measurement and kinetic analysis, the two parameter autocatalytic model given from Sestak-Berggren is the most suitable model to adhesive for rapid repair. The kinetic mechanism function shows a perfect agreement with the experiment curves. Therefore, this model will provide a vital theory in polymer material compose process of adhesive for rapid repair.

Reference

1. Zhen Dai, Yanfang Li, Shuguang Yang, et al, Kinetics and Thermal Properties of Epoxy Resins Based on Bishenol Fluorene Structure. *European Polymer Journal*, 45(2009) 1941-1948
2. ZHANG Chun-Ling, Mu Jian-Xin, Yu Wen-Zhi, et al, Curing Reaction Kinetics of Epoxy Resin Containing Biphenyl Structure Using DDS as Curing Agent. *Chemical Journal of Chinese Universities*, Vol.25 No.10, 1937-1940, 2004
3. ZHANG Chun-ling, NA Hui, LIU Chen-guang, et al, Synthesis and Demonstration of Diglycidyl Ether Epoxy Resin Containing Biphenyl. *Thermosetting Resin*, Vol.17 No.1, 1-3, 2002
4. Shao-ping Ren, Yan-xun Lan, Yi-quan Zhen, et al, Curing Reaction Characteristics and Phase Behaviors of Biphenol Type Epoxy Resins with Phenol Novolac Resin. *Thermochimica acta*, 440 (2006) 60-67
5. CUI Jin-wen, WANG Shu-hong, ZHANG Rui-ren, et al, Preparation and Curing Reaction Kinetics of Epoxy Resin Containing Biphenyl Structure/Montmorillonite Nanocomposites. *Journal of Jilin University(Science Edition)*, Vol.49 No.5, 939-943, 2011